

DIAMAS

Developing Institutional Open Access
Publishing Models to Advance
Scholarly Communication

Consider your options: explore the different funding streams for Diamond Open Access

This guide lists the different funding or revenue stream options available to Diamond publishers and service providers. It will help them navigate the different options available and in understanding the pros and cons of each, and assist them in deciding which is most suitable for their field, business model, and size.

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Introduction

This guide lists the different funding and revenue stream options available to Diamond Open Access (OA) publishers and service providers. We hope it will help them navigate the different options available, understand the pros and cons of each, and assist them in deciding which is most suitable for their field, business model, and size.

Some of these options are well-established, while others are new and/or under development and offer promising alternatives. Diamond OA publishers or service providers may combine some options to remain sustainable and strong in the long term.

Note that the Diamond OA publishing model is agnostic with respect to the sources of revenue that support and sustain a Diamond OA publisher's operations, as long as transparency of funding is provided and authors aren't charged any obligatory fees (in line with section 1.2 of the [Diamond OA Standard](#)), and the journal fulfils the six operational criteria for Diamond OA (<https://diamasproject.eu/operational-diamond-oa-criteria-for-journals/>).

This guide primarily (but not exclusively) focuses on journals, listing funding streams that are currently used or could be useful for journal publishers and service providers. However, book publishers may also find some of these options relevant, and in certain cases, examples of book funding streams are included.

While this list aims to be comprehensive, it is not exhaustive. Some existing models may be omitted, particularly those that blend elements of multiple approaches (e.g. the [Lyrasis OACIP](#) model, which incorporates aspects of both the *Collective Pledging model* and *Collective Supporter programs*). Publishers and service providers are encouraged to use these models as inspiration for further development and innovation.

If you are aware of other funding streams or models not covered here, please share the information and relevant links by emailing toolsuite@diamas.org.

Funding Diamond OA: find the funding or revenue source most suitable for you

This list describes the most important funding mechanisms for Diamond OA publishers and service providers. Please note that:

- Only the options compatible with Diamond OA are listed and described.
- Options that are incompatible with Diamond OA, such as Article Processing Charges (APCs), Book Processing Charges (BPCs), online subscriptions for access, and pay-per-view, are omitted.
- Some options could be considered as “conditionally” Diamond OA (e.g., Subscribe to Open (S2O)), where content becomes Diamond OA if certain conditions are fulfilled, most importantly the condition of community ownership.
- Novel and emerging types of revenue sources are also included.

Description of resource options

(in alphabetical order)

[Collective pledging model](#)

[Collective supporter programmes](#)

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Collective pledging model

Description: Publications, publishing services and infrastructures can become beneficiaries of schemes that organise collective pledging campaigns to raise small amounts of funds to reach a specific funding target through collective funding. This works similarly to crowdfunding. Organisations interested in supporting these publications, services or infrastructures can make pledges in the form of commitments to financially contribute to the development or operations of these publishing services and infrastructures for a specified period of time. Publications, services and infrastructures wishing to be eligible for such campaigns may need to fulfil quality criteria related to their value, publishing and editorial procedures, governance structure, costs, sustainability measures, or future plans. They need to define a realistic pledging goal. The collective pledging model typically requires an intermediary organisation that will organise campaigns, define the criteria for eligibility, and select the candidates for pledging campaigns.

Funded: A publication, a publisher, a service provider or an infrastructure

Funder/resource provider: Libraries, institutions, consortia, governments, research funding agencies, and other organisations in scholarly communication.

Examples: [The Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services \(SCOSS\)](#), and the [KOALA Consortium service at the TIB - Leibniz Information Centre for Science and Technology University Library](#).

Who it is appropriate for: Existing Diamond OA publishers, publishing service providers, and infrastructures that provide a valuable service to a dedicated community of users who need additional funding to consolidate and develop their operations.

Pros: This type of time-delimited funding can provide financial security for organisations that already have a certain level of maturity and can set clear goals for further development. It can also help build new partnerships between services or infrastructures and pledging institutions, including developing their governance. This model can be applied at different scales, from supporting a collection of a few journals to sustaining globally relevant infrastructures.

Cons: Publishers, publishing service providers, and infrastructures with less maturity will have difficulties fulfilling the quality criteria required to be eligible for the pledging mechanism. Those less recognised among the user communities will have more difficulties attracting enough contributing institutions to reach their pledging targets.

Collective supporter programmes

Description: This model is similar to the *Library membership programme* and refers to a group of publishers and/or service providers organised in a consortium (a collective) that jointly seeks support from libraries in the form of supporting membership fees. Publishing outputs are Diamond OA, i.e. available to all and not only to members. Membership fees enable the continuation and development of publishing services. It is similar to the *Library membership programme*, except that publishers are not seeking memberships individually but as a collective. Aside from jointly seeking funding, collective members can collaborate in other domains of the publishing process and exchange expertise and experiences.

Funded: A consortium of publishers and/or service providers.

Funder/resource provider: Libraries (or institutions) and research funding agencies.

Examples: [Open Book Collective](#)/[ScholarLed Consortium](#)

Who it is appropriate for: This model is especially relevant for Diamond OA publishers who already have established contacts with other publishers and service providers with similar audiences and publishing profiles in terms of size, language or topics. This type of consortium is typically established as an informal group of members with a shared background and focus, organisation type, or place of origin.

Pros: Diamond OA publishers and service providers can act more efficiently if they act together by e.g. pooling resources and capacity. Members of Diamond OA consortia will benefit from jointly running activities related to fundraising, outreach, marketing, and financial administration. Aside from jointly acquired memberships, participating Diamond OA publishers are also allowed to continue their own individual membership programmes. Consortial offers are more likely to be appealing to potential member libraries.

Cons: Diamond OA consortium members must find a fair way to distribute the collected membership funds. This may become challenging when members develop at different paces or in different directions, affecting the size and content of their publishing portfolios. Publishers with unique profiles or isolated publishers could have difficulty finding a collective they can join or establish. Publishers from areas where libraries are underfunded, lack OA funds, or the support from university managers to invest in open content will have difficulties attracting enough members: the effort in doing so may require too many resources compared to expected benefits.

Cooperative centralised funding

Description: In some scholarly disciplines, multiple institutions interested in enabling open and barrier-free publishing can form a consortium to fund publications relevant to their field. This consortial funding covers publication costs for a selected collection of journals or books. One institution manages payments and centrally collects funds from participating institutions. The total contribution from each country, region, or territory is proportional to its share of global scientific output in the field and fairly reflects global diversity to ensure an equitable distribution of publication costs across all participants. Although the costs for participating institutions are calculated based on APCs, this model has no fees for authors or readers, regardless of their institutional affiliation. However, participating journals are only fully Diamond OA if they are community-owned in the sense of the six operational criteria for Diamond OA (<https://diamasproject.eu/operational-diamond-oa-criteria-for-journals/>).

Funded: A selection of journals and books relevant to a specific scholarly field.

Funder/resource provider: Libraries, funding agencies, and research centres coordinated by a designated institution.

Examples: [SCOAP³](#) - Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics.

Who it is appropriate for: This funding model is particularly suited to scholarly fields with strong international collaborations and significant financial revenues, where researchers form well-connected global communities.

Pros: This model allows all authors worldwide to publish in OA without financial or administrative barriers by providing centralised funding for selected journals. It facilitates global knowledge exchange within a research field and enhances communication and collaboration among researchers.

Cons: In some research fields, organising institutions globally into a consortium of this kind can be extremely challenging because of the dispersed and fragmented nature of many scholarly disciplines.

Donations and grants from private funders or charities

Description: Similar to public bodies, certain private funders and charities may fund Diamond OA publishers, journals, or service providers and infrastructures. Such funding can be made available via calls where funding is awarded to those who fulfil the required criteria. The organisation and requirements of such calls can vary depending on the criteria and goals set by the charity. Alternatively, the charity can decide to fund a project or a beneficiary that aligns well with its mission.

Funded: Journals, publishers or platforms

Funder/resource provider: Private funder or charity

Examples: [Collaboration for sustainable open access publishing in Africa](#) (funded by Wellcome), OA grants by [Arcadia Fund](#)

Who it is appropriate for: Journals, publishers and platforms aligned with the charity's mission and eligible according to its criteria.

Pros: Philanthropic grants are viable and useful funding mechanisms for developing new services, fostering innovation, or transitioning existing publishing operations and services to open business models.

Cons: Philanthropic grants are most often awarded as one-time grants and do not provide long-term sustainability.

Individual membership fees

Description: Different types of organisations—most commonly learned societies and professional associations—can collect fees from their members and use them to support their publishing activities. Membership in such an organisation can offer researchers various benefits, some of which relate to publishing (e.g., receiving a free subscription to print copies of a journal, if print versions still exist, or receiving regular updates and tables of contents for online editions). As long as publishing in such a community-owned journal is not conditional on membership or APCs, this model is in line with conditions for Diamond OA publishing.

Funded: An organisation with a publishing activity or runs a publishing service.

Funder/resource provider: Individuals - members of an organisation or an association

Examples: [European Societies](#) – a journal published by MIT Press, owned and supported by the umbrella membership organisation – the [European Sociological Association](#); [Revija za sociologiju](#) – a journal published by the [Croatian Sociological Association](#) (a national association and a member of the European Sociological Association)

Who it is appropriate for: This type of funding is particularly suited to organisations (primarily societies or associations) with a strong membership base that forms a dedicated community, either at a national or international level. It can be used to convert an existing non-Diamond journal to the Diamond OA model or to establish a new journal, as well as other types of publishing outlets or services.

Pros: For organisations with dedicated members, this type of funding provides a stable and reliable source of income. Member support can extend beyond financial contributions to include in-kind or voluntary efforts, such as editorial work, quality control, or governance.

Cons: In organisations that publish multiple journals or have additional activities requiring financial support, allocating income from membership fees can become challenging.

Library membership programmes

Description: Diamond OA publishers can offer libraries an opportunity to support their work through library membership programmes. They can offer library-specific tiered fees or allow libraries to decide on the amount they wish to allocate for this membership. Publishers can also provide special benefits for library members (for instance, discounts on purchases of print copies for libraries or their users, regular usage statistics or providing MARC records for library catalogues). Libraries are more likely to support publishers and publishing services if they know their users and university management find them valuable. To facilitate this, Diamond OA publishers can collect evidence of publications by researchers affiliated with a given institution and present it to the institution's library when seeking support. Publishing platforms and service providers can also apply for this revenue source.

Funded: A publisher or a service provider

Funder/resource provider: Libraries (or institutions)

Examples: Open Book Publishers

(<https://www.openbookpublishers.com/libraries/benefits-and-information>); the consortial library model of the [Open Library of Humanities](#).

Who it is appropriate for: Diamond OA publishers or service providers with a dedicated community of libraries, publishers who know about the groups of libraries interested in their collections, and publishers who have staff and resources for supporting and maintaining the community of library members and reaching new ones. It is easier to gain support from libraries whose users are also active users or whose authors publish with the publisher or service provider.

Pros: This income can provide a regular and potentially stable annual revenue stream. It contributes to the visibility of publishers and their publications through cooperation with libraries and strengthens their role in the scholarly communication chain.

Cons: Library outreach activities can be resource-demanding and require specific expertise. Publishers with smaller or specialised portfolios (regarding language, topic, or type of publication) can have more difficulties in attracting a substantial number of library supporters.

Sales of additional digital content or services (Freemium)

Description: A combination of the words “free” and “premium,” freemium is a business model that offers basic products or services to users openly at no cost but charges a premium for supplementary or advanced features. In this model, OA content is disseminated freely and is complemented by premium services and formats available exclusively to institutions and their users. For instance, the HTML format can be available as OA, while users of partner institutions can download the PDF and ePub formats (still, without DRM or download quotas). Different purchasing options for premium formats, e.g. permanent purchases, rental options, and annual subscriptions, can be offered.

Funded: Individual publication titles (journals or books) or collections of titles

Funder/resource provider: Libraries/institutions

Examples: [OpenEdition Freemium for Books](#), [OpenEdition Freemium for Journals](#)

Who it is appropriate for: The model is suitable for publishers with available publishing platforms and technical capabilities for offering additional services that can be charged for in addition to the availability of content in basic formats. This type of income is also

more appropriate for publishers with a more diverse and substantial catalogue of book or journal collections and less for small publishers, for instance, single journal publishers.

Pros: While providing the content in OA, publishers with freemium programmes will still have an array of subscriber-only services that can be attractive to users and libraries, so that the income from these subscriptions can contribute to their sustainability. Offers of collections that include titles of multiple publishers can additionally be attractive to libraries, especially since the freemium content will be easily integrated into the library catalogues and discovery tools.

Cons: Publishers need to use the services of platforms capable of operating the freemium programme, and using these platforms is not free of charge. Publishers need to balance the investment for using the platform with the expected income and increase in the visibility that will result from the platform use. Also, though non-subscribed users are still able to access full-text open content, it may not be available to them in their preferred format (they will have to use HTML instead of PDF or ePub, for instance).

Sales of print copies

Description: Selling print copies of OA publications is a revenue source that is still viable for many publishers, primarily book publishers, and sometimes even journal publishers. This can be achieved by printing publications in traditional print runs or using print-on-demand services. As long as online versions of works are available as immediate OA editions, selling print counterparts does not conflict with Diamond OA.

Funded: A publication (a book or a journal issue) or a collection of publications.

Funder/resource provider: Individual readers or academic libraries.

Examples: [Bern Open Publishing](#), [BMGN - Low Countries Historical Review](#)

Who it is appropriate for: This type of funding can serve as a source of income for publishers who continue to have an audience for print editions (especially audiences that are outside of academia and without access to collective subscriptions). Those are often publishers of books in humanities and social sciences or journals with readers among professionals and practitioners, for instance, in law, healthcare, etc.

Pros: Many academics remain committed to reading in print and are willing to buy print copies of publications, especially books, even when they can access OA digital editions.

In such cases, the availability of Diamond OA editions can even boost print sales, providing a stable income for publishers.

Cons: In many domains, interest in print, and the selling of print copies is declining. If that is the case, producing print copies can even lead to losses, instead of earnings. In such cases, print-on-demand can be one possible solution, while in other instances, discarding print entirely and focusing only on digital editions may be the best option.

Subscribe to Open (S2O)

Description: S2O is a subscription model that allows a publisher to convert journals from gated access to OA. Institutional subscription revenue is collected as normal and assuming all subscribers participate, the publisher commits to publishing that year's content OA. This is considered a subscription model, not a voluntary donation. S2O requires all of a journal's existing subscribers to participate. If one or more subscribers opt out of the offer, the publisher has the right to retract the offer and keep that year's content gated. Any library opting out of the offer would need a subscription to access the content. Publishers take into account the normal price variations of subscriptions. Publishers of S2O journals do not offer an APC route to authors in case the threshold for OA isn't met and the journal remains in closed access. Authors can comply with OA mandates using the green route in such cases. Note that S2O journals are Diamond OA journals when the journal title is community-owned and complies with the six operational criteria of Diamond OA (see criterium 6 of the six operational criteria for Diamond OA (<https://diamasproject.eu/operational-diamond-oa-criteria-for-journals/>)). Diamond OA is agnostic with respect to the source of revenue that sustains the journal's operations, as long as transparency of funding is provided, which is in line with section 1.2 of the [Diamond OA Standard](#).

Funded: Individual journal titles or journal collections.

Funder/resource provider: Libraries/institutions previously subscribing to a journal/collection while it was in closed access.

Examples: [Annual Reviews](#), [Project Muse](#), [De Gruyter](#)

Who it is appropriate for: S2O works best for established subscription journals with stable subscriber bases. In most cases, it would not be as well-suited to new subscription journals with growing subscriber bases, journals that experience significant variations in the price of subscription from year-to-year, existing OA journals, and journals that depend on significant non-subscription revenue (from licensing, advertising, etc.).

Pros: For well-established journals with a stable subscriber base, S2O offers a transparent transition to OA with little disruption to the current process and no additional cost to subscribers. It can be seen as a transitional model for journals that are not able to find immediate funding from other sources and want to rely on a steady income. It is an equitable option since it enables all authors, regardless of the institution they are affiliated with, to continue publishing in their preferred journal without paying APCs.

Cons: The main drawback of this option is the conditional nature of OA; until all of the existing subscribers agree to continue their subscriptions, and the subscription threshold is met, it is not certain that the journal will actually be available openly.

Subscriptions to print copies

Description: Subscriptions to print copies of OA publications are one possible revenue source for Diamond OA publishers of serial publications. This could be achieved either by printing publications in traditional print runs or by using print-on-demand services. As long as online versions of works are available as OA editions without any delays, subscriptions to print counterparts do not conflict with Diamond OA.

Target of funding: A serial publication (a journal, a collection of journals, or other serial publications).

Funded: Individual readers or academic libraries.

Examples: Almost all Diamond OA journals that are not born digital and have not yet abandoned the print version, sell subscriptions to print copies.

Who is it appropriate for: This kind of funding is most suited to publishers that still have a traditional audience for print editions (especially audiences that are outside of academia and without access to collective subscriptions), such as publishers of book series in humanities and social sciences or journals that have readers among professionals and practitioners, for instance in law, healthcare, etc.

Pros: Many academics prefer reading in print, and their libraries are willing to subscribe to print copies of publications, especially book series.

Cons: In many domains, interest in print is declining. If that is the case, producing print copies can even lead to losses instead of earnings. In such cases, print-on-demand can be one possible solution, while discarding print entirely and focusing only on digital editions can be the best option in other cases.

Subsidies and grants from public bodies

Description: Public bodies (governments, ministries, national research agencies or funders and similar) can provide funding for publishers (or individual journals) through regular and periodical public calls or project grants, upon which funding is awarded to those that fulfil the required criteria. There are different ways that these public calls can be organised and other ways to define the criteria based on the concepts of quality that prevail in a specific context or the goals set by the funder. Those goals could be, for instance, to support non-profit publishing, to support Diamond OA publishers and service providers, to enable existing journals to transition to OA, or to preserve publishing in a specific language and/or specific discipline. Some existing public schemes are more beneficial to publishers and service providers depending on their timeframes. Longer-term grants and subsidies are generally preferred, as short-term funding is more complex and costly to manage and provides less stability for recipients.

Funded: Journals, publishers or platforms (operating in a country and eligible according to the proposed criteria)

Funder/resource provider: Public bodies (governments, ministries, national research funders)

Examples: Governmental public funding subsidy for non-profit journals that is distributed by TSV in Finland; the Belgian Fund for Scientific Research, which provides annual calls for journal publishers, granting subsidies for up to three-year periods, the Norwegian NÅHST model, and the French National Open Science Fund.

Who is it appropriate for: Journals, publishers and platforms that are eligible according to the proposed criteria. Except for the French National Open Science Fund, most other current subsidy schemes are nationally bounded, meaning only entities based in a certain country are eligible. That means journals, publishers or platforms based in countries without established and available subsidy schemes cannot rely on this funding source.

Pros: If the calls for subsidies are periodical but regular, publishers can rely on them as a stable and reliable source of funding.

Cons: Eligibility criteria for receiving public subsidies are not always fully aligned with the principles of Diamond OA. The received subsidies are not always sufficient for regular operations and/or for developmental tasks of a journal/publisher. There may be issues with the timelines for allocating subsidies, and grants or subsidies provided on a short-term basis do not offer long-term stability or sustainability. Public bodies can

unilaterally decide to discontinue specific funding streams due to political changes or budget cuts. This means that publishers cannot entirely rely on them as a stable funding mechanism. Most countries do not have a dedicated public subsidy scheme for Diamond OA publishing.

Voluntary author contributions (VACs)

Description: Some publishers and their journals may recommend that authors with institutional funds or grant funding dedicated to OA publication cover the costs of their article publication. The journal should be transparent about the publishing cost and provide the VAC fee based on the actual costs. The VAC should be genuinely voluntary, and the ability to pay the VAC should not impact the editorial procedures or decisions related to the article.

Funded: A publication unit (article or chapter)

Funder/resource provider: Authors or authors' institutions

Examples: Publications of [Open Library of Humanities](#) and the journal [Glossa Psycholinguistics at eScholarship](#).

Who is it appropriate for: All publishers who publish at least a proportion of articles/chapters resulting from funded research projects or whose authors have dedicated institutional OA funds.

Pros: VACs, when authors can make them, can cover publication costs of a share of published articles (e.g. editorial processes, web hosting, indexing, marketing, archiving, DOI registration, etc.) and contribute to the publishers' sustainability. This allows those who can afford to contribute a VAC to do so while not excluding those who cannot. In that way, those who can pay contribute to building a more equitable and inclusive publishing system.

Cons: VACs are not likely to suffice for a journal's overall financial need and they will need to be supplemented by other funding sources. They also mostly work in disciplines where authors have grant money at their disposal for this purpose. They represent a considerable administrative burden for larger journals in exchange for relatively small sums, especially when each payment system has its own requirements for paying the VAC.

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Further reading

Open Access Journals Toolkit. <https://www.oajournals-toolkit.org/>

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Business Models for Open Access Books. <https://oabooksbusinessmodels.pubpub.org/>

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